

DBB Contract Management Modeling With System Dynamics Approach in Therapeutic Projects

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ABSTRACT: The aim of the current research is to model the improvement of DBB contract claims management with the system dynamics approach in treatment projects. In this research, in order to properly understand the relationships between the variables affecting the claims in order to reduce them in the complex space of the projects, the system dynamics method was used to better understand the cause and effect relationships between them. The statistical population in the present study were experts such as educational professors and supervisors of therapeutic projects, of which 3 were selected as educational professors and 12 were supervisors of therapeutic projects. Systems dynamics methodology was used for data analysis and "Vensim" software was used for simulation. After formulating the dynamic hypothesis, an initial causal-disability model was extracted and then this model was discussed with the stakeholders and experts of the studied projects and their opinions were obtained through in-depth semi-structured interviews. After the approval of the flow chart of the model by the practitioners and experts, and the model validation tests, simulation was performed and the effect of different policies was investigated and analyzed, and the behavior of the system was studied under different scenarios, and at the end, the findings of the analysis Various policies and system behavior studies were discussed.

Keywords: DBB Contracts, System Dynamics, Treatment Projects

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1. Introduction

Claims have become an inherent feature of the construction industry. In order to identify claims and their components, various studies have been conducted in different countries. Another research has been done in the field of claim reduction, such as providing solutions, using expert systems and operating systems, using complete and explicit contracts, and paying attention to the soft factors of project management, such as building trust, communication, partnership and cooperation, but they are still. They are common in the construction industry of the world and especially in Iran, which shows the importance of paying attention to this issue. By studying the literature on the subject, it was found that most of the studies conducted around claims have several knowledge gaps, such as not paying attention to claims in any type of project and with a unique project implementation system, not separating claim components in identifying claims, and finally, not paying attention to causal relationships between claims in each project. The issue of treatment is considered one of the most important issues of today's societies, and with the progress of science and human knowledge, the complexity of this issue increases every day. Therefore, the reduction of claims during the construction of hospital projects, which is one of the main concerns of the country's medical sciences universities, is of particular importance, and the timely exploitation of these types of projects can include reducing costs and increasing quality. On the one hand, considering the importance and recent expansion of the construction of medical projects in the country, especially in the field of building and equipping hospitals, and on the other hand, considering the existence of many claims in these projects, the main goal of this research is to reduce the contractor's claims in this type of projects, especially in the fields of time and cost that are overwhelmingly, all of them are contracted as three factors. Today, due to the lack of financial resources, the need to save time and money is felt more and more. One of the problems that endangers the time management of the construction of a hospital is the occurrence of claims in the construction of such projects, and these claims are a result of losses. It does not work for employers, contractors and beneficiaries, and it causes the waste of financial resources and prolongs the construction of hospital projects. In order to properly understand the relationships between variables affecting claims in order to reduce them in the complex space of projects, the system dynamics method will be used to better understand the cause and effect relationships between them; which is a comprehensive method and a complete tool for studying the behavior of complex systems.

2. Statement of the problem

The construction industry is one of the main economic sectors of Iran, which plays an important role in creating job opportunities and economic growth of the country. It can be said that the progress, prosperity and excellence of a nation depends a lot on the success of its country's construction projects. In recent years, investment plans have widely appropriated capital and other national resources. The country's management and planning organization and therefore the success of these projects play an important role in the country's economy. Construction projects often account for 7 to 10 percent of the GDP, so it can be said that it is the economic backbone of many countries. Because all the members of the society have come to the conclusion from the processes and products of different

researchers that the most important research flow in this connection is dedicated to the field of vital factors of project success. There are also many contracts in the field of construction, one of which is DBB. Claim management is one of the most important topics and challenges of projects in the world, which many project beneficiaries consider to be one of the most destructive events in the construction industry. In this regard, the current research is trying to use the system dynamics approach to reduce the contractor's claims in the field of projects carried out by the three-factor DBB method in the treatment (hospital) projects of the country in order to reduce the time and cost caused by their claims. In evaluating the success of construction projects as one of the characteristics of the economic development of any country, the three main parameters of time, cost and quality are usually used as the golden triangle; And various factors affect them. In the meantime, factors that seem invisible may have a more important and prominent role. One of these invisible factors are claims. In most projects and with different implementation methods, there is a possibility of claims from the project parties, especially contractors. Of course, in recent years, due to the problems of financing the construction of medical projects, the problem of claims has also increased in such projects. Anshasi et al. believe that project completion is without a doubt a key factor for a successful construction project. Because the main source of cost and overflow time, according to the research of most researchers in the world, including Nigeria, are related to claims. Therefore, by removing the claim, it is possible to increase the related time and cost performance in the construction projects and their success. In order to reduce and prevent claims, a lot of research has been done by researchers from different countries, but they are still common. Probably the reason for this is the need to better understand the complexity between the causal variables of making claims in the complex environment of projects. Once this understanding is established, then strategies and processes can be put in place to prevent them from happening in the first place. By looking at the literature in this field, one can find research that focuses on the soft aspects of project success factors instead of focusing on the technical and hard aspects of the project success factors. In order to reduce and prevent the occurrence of claims, research has been done in the field of claim reduction, such as identifying claims, providing solutions, using systems, using contracts, and paying attention to the soft factors of project management, including building trust, by researchers from different countries. Most of the research has been done in developing countries and the need to reduce claims is felt more in these countries. Looking at the purpose of the research, it is clear that there is little understanding of the components of the claim package among the researchers, and the separation of the cause from the origin and demand has not been done correctly. In most of the researches about the claim, the researcher has examined the contractor's claims from the perspective of the employer. In the end, the research field of most researchers has been general; Because the claims are different in each specific type of projects and also in each project implementation system, and little research is observed in this regard; Especially, there is no research in the area of medical project claims and considering their increasing importance, especially in the current conditions of Iran. It should be noted that considering the construction of the country's treatment projects using the DBB three-factor method and considering the necessity of the hospital issue and the importance of the project's time and cost performance and the high amount of contracts and the existence of many claims in it, in this research the country's hospitals will be reviewed. In such projects, the employer concludes a contract for the construction, completion and equipping of the

hospital with the contractor and assigns the responsibility of design and supervision to the consultant. Due to rework and changes by the employer, the claim of increased cost due to increased time due to permitted delays. Therefore, in the current research, the question is to be answered, what is the modeling of improving the management of DBB contract claims with the approach of system dynamics in treatment projects?

3. Research Questions

The current research was done in order to model the improvement of DBB contract claims management with the system dynamics approach in treatment projects. This research was done to answer these questions:

- What are the main factors of dispute in three-factor contracts for the construction of hospitals that lead to claims?
- How is the dynamic model of claims system in DBB contracts?

4. Research Background

Kanani (2018) in a research on the management of lawsuits and claims in the project with the perspective of private and urban constructions, the purpose of this article is to learn how to prevent common problems in procurement and resolve disputes between the employer and the contractor and, as a result, reduce time And the cost is to increase the efficiency and profitability of the project and achieve the desired benefits for the parties. In this direction, in order to reach a practical and step-by-step solution and according to the requirements and time limit of the discussion, firstly, in the first part, the basic concepts will be introduced very briefly, and then in the second part, the existing challenges and their roots will be examined. Next and relying on them in the third part, the requirements, steps and processes necessary for the optimal management of contracts and contractors in the project and reduction of lawsuits, claims (claims) and disputes between the employer and the contractor will be discussed. Dana (2018) in a research entitled management of claims in projects, according to the existing standards, has reached the conclusion that in these years, the increase in constructions has caused a large amount of credits to be consumed annually in this way, and on the other hand, it also faces problems. For various reasons, the parties may object to the laws. In public and private projects, this is possible, the increase in inflation, lack of liquidity and other similar factors can be the factors that cause it. Amani et al. (2018) in a research titled identifying the factors of claims in Iranian construction projects with the approach of three-factor contracts, have reached the conclusion that a significant part of the most frequent factors in the basic research is related to the employer. It was also found that some factors of the occurrence of claims in Iran are different from the results obtained from the analysis of the base research, according to the conditions governing the country's projects. Parkhami and Moradi (2018) in a research titled Claims Management Office, a solution for implementing claim management processes in the contractor-oriented construction industry, concluded that one of the biggest challenges in the construction industry is claim management in projects. Correct implementation of claim management processes is one of the ways to overcome these challenges. But there are many problems in implementing these processes in the project. One of the most important solutions

obtained in this research is employing experts in the subject of claims and using them in an institution called the Claims Management Office in the project. Baqarpour and Mousavi (2017) in a research entitled providing an interpretative structural model for claim management in construction projects have reached the conclusion that the four reasons for choosing a contractor based on lower price and without considering technical competence and ability, the low price of the contract due to competition Above, ambiguity and contradiction in the documents or provisions of the contract and sudden and unexpected changes in the exchange rate and bank interest have the highest influence and influence on other causes and as a result have the highest importance in reducing and preventing the occurrence of claims. Taheripour et al. (2017) in a research entitled Factors of Claims in Construction Plan Projects and Solutions to Reduce Them (Case Study: Civil-Subsurface Projects in Tehran) reached the conclusion that the implementation of projects by the construction plan method in the country compared to the implementation systems The existing project is newly emerged and the parties to the agreement have little familiarity with it; For this reason, the occurrence of differences between these factors, especially in subsurface projects that have a complex nature, will be inevitable. Salmani and Qurbani (2017) in a research titled claims management and identification of the main causes of claims in construction projects, reached the conclusion that among the most important issues and challenges that threaten the process of project implementation is the occurrence of claims in construction projects, which results such as breaking It will include relations, parties' differences and the most important delay in the project. In most projects, there is a possibility of claims from agents, especially contractors. These claims have negative effects on the implementation of projects. Although the possibility of these claims cannot be eliminated in any project, they can be largely prevented from occurring in future projects by identifying the main causes of claims. Farahani Hemmati M et al. (2022) the analysis is done by summarizing the critical field points and research estimates of technical and financial capacities based on the results of the project and the research literature.

Ansari et al. (2017) in a research titled Analytical investigation of the main factors of the event and claims management process in the construction industry of Iran and other countries reached the conclusion that although it is not possible to completely eliminate the possibility of claims in projects, it can be Identifying its causes and examining the history of this category in previous projects largely prevented its occurrence. Certainly, preventing the occurrence of a dispute is much simpler and less expensive than resolving a dispute. If the causes of contractual disputes are known, it can be said that the ways to prevent them will also be known. Parchami, Jalal and Samani (2017) in a research titled "Investigation of the use of dispute resolution committees (DB) in the process of project claims management" reached the conclusion that in some projects, various types of dispute resolution committees² have been used to speed up the dispute resolution process, which the studies indicate The success of this method in the process of resolving claims is compared to the common methods in the mentioned projects. This process is known to be very common in some parts of the world, but unfortunately, many of the beneficiaries of the project, especially in the Middle East countries, have not benefited from the benefits of using this method due to insufficient knowledge of this method. The purpose of this article is to briefly introduce these committees, to review their history, and to examine the necessity and benefits of using this method. It is also predicted that the use of these committees will soon

play an important role in the construction industry. In a research, Parchami et al. (2014) have compiled the algorithm of legal-contractual claims and evaluated their frequency and intensity in the non-industrial design and construction projects of the country. Some of the important findings of this study are the classification of the claims of the non-industrial design and construction projects of the country from the perspective of The degree of ambiguity and transparency is for them.

Parchami Jalal and Mohrhari (2020) in a research entitled providing a model for preparing optimal contracts to prevent claims in projects, the main reasons for the increase of claims in projects are identified using the library research method and document analysis method. Then, by complementing and combining related models, adding a communication agent as a contributing factor, and providing a training bank of contractual knowledge, a new model is presented that can help in preparing optimal contracts and thereby effectively either reducing or preventing claims. Zhou et al. (2020) in a research titled simulation of construction project delivery system decision under sustainable construction project management have reached the conclusion that based on multi-agent systems (MAS), they built a decision simulation model for project delivery system decision making. Deciding on the project delivery system. When analyzing the conditions under which owners tend to choose DB or DBB, they reached the following conclusions: (1) the contractor's technology and capabilities increase faster in DB than in DBB; (2) The project delivery system with policy and market settings has the decision advantage of the project delivery system, and the owners are more willing to choose the project delivery system that was previously chosen. (3) The mechanism of competition in the construction market will eliminate contractors whose growth rate is too low to meet the needs of projects in the market. Lee and Borman (2020) in a research entitled Building Information Modeling and Construction Management have concluded that Building Information Modeling can give the client the possibility to match the designs offered by design companies and institutions with safety, fire address, lighting, energy issues and issue 11, construction and coordination costs and confirm or reject it. After this, the employer can conduct a correct and clear tender.

Lindhard and Larsen (2020) in a research titled identifying the key factors affecting the performance of the construction project have reached the conclusion that a construction project traditionally involves different participants. Owners, consultants and contractors all have different opinions and interests, but they are all looking to ensure the success of the project. Success is typically measured as performance output in terms of cost, time, and quality. The emergence of a claim in a construction project can greatly reduce the performance of the construction project and slow down the project, so it is necessary to adopt claims management approaches. Mota et al. (2019) in a research entitled Building Information Modeling for Production: Advantages and Challenges for Application in DBB Projects have reached the conclusion that the effective use of Building Information Modeling has a positive effect on the speed of DBB projects, therefore for Building Information Modeling A skilled professional with design and construction knowledge is needed. Rostgari et al. (2019) in a research entitled a presentation of a model to determine the optimal strategy for resolving claims in construction projects have reached the conclusion that this model includes the strategies of the contractor and the owner in a four-stage process including: negotiation, mediation, It investigates arbitration and disputes. This

helps the involved parties to have a deeper understanding of the problem, to have a better assessment of their situation and to analyze possible strategies in facing such a situation. By considering different scenarios, points that both parties can reasonably agree on are presented with an analytical solution. Finally, two cases of real-world problems are presented and analyzed using the proposed method, and the optimal strategy is determined for each case.

Nicoletta and Augustin (2018) in a research titled Legal Consequences of Using Building Information Modeling (BIM) concluded that the legal consequences of adopting BIM in construction projects is one of the recently discussed issues that are not yet fully understood and risk mitigation measures are also It is not followed in this direction. This research aims to emphasize some of the legal concepts of adopting BIM in relation to procurement and contracting strategies. In this article, it is concluded that BIM is expected to create more transparency in the implementation of the construction project and enable a more comprehensive and transparent audit that leads to less legal disputes. Farahani, Mehrab Hemmati, et al. (2024) The purpose of this article is to increase the understanding of how design companies understand the benefits of using building information modeling technologies. Building information modeling has been recognized in the literature as a (potential) powerful driver that moves the construction sector towards sustainability. However, for design firms, the choice to invest in building information modeling technologies is primarily an economic one. John et al. (2018) in a research entitled the impact of building information modeling (BIM) on construction performance concluded that the findings and recommendations of this study can be used by companies to assess their current BIM adoption and identify whether BIM should be used. be used These findings also identify areas in the BIM infrastructure that need improvement to more positively impact construction performance. Hemmati Farahani M ,et al. (2023) Policymakers are the other governing stakeholders who empower all stakeholders on system applications. It was observed that the role of policymakers is significant to strength the other stakeholders and expansion. Taghipour et al. (2016) studied "The impact of ICT on knowledge sharing obstacles in knowledge management process (including case-study)." Mohammad et al. Jamshidi and Hatef (2016) in a research titled identifying the reasons for contractors' claims in D-B-B contracts and evaluating them by multi-criteria decision-making models (AHP) reached the conclusion that in most projects using different delivery systems, entities, especially contractors, may claim do In addition, claims and disagreements are inevitable in Bid Design projects, especially in Design-Bid-Build (D-B-B) contracts, which are not commonly used in Iran. The focus of this study is the causes of claims raised in projects delivered by Design-Bid-Build (D-B-B) contracts. In other research, the following can be mentioned: Taghipour et al.(2015) studied "Risk analysis in the management of urban construction projects from the perspective of the employer and the contractor." (2015) studied "Assessing the effect of the FRP system on compressive and shear bending strength of concrete elements." Jalili et al. (2015) studied "Comparative study of Khaje Rashid al-Din views on Rab-e Rashidi Islamic Utopia and Kevin Lynch ideas." Rezvani et al.(2015) discussed "The design of high-rise building with ecological approach in Iran (Alborz Province)." Taghipour and Yazdi(2015) studied "Seismic analysis (non-linear static analysis (pushover) and nonlinear dynamic) on Cable-Stayed Bridge."

5. Statistical Population and Sampling

The statistical population in the present study were experts such as educational professors and supervisors of therapeutic projects, of which 3 were selected as educational professors and 12 were supervisors of therapeutic projects. which are selected in an accessible manner.

Table 1- The members of the sample size in the present study

Percent	Abundance	Sample
20	3	Educational professors
80	12	Treatment project supervisor
100	15	Total

6. Scope of Research

A) Spatial territory: The place of conducting the research of the three-factor projects of the country's hospitals.

6.1. The statistical population of the research

Managers of project control and handling contracts, contracts, CEOs and project managers of employer organizations, consultants, contractors and other agents who are experts in the discussion of claims in the project under study, experts and have at least 5 years of experience as stakeholders and experts, society Statistics form this research

7. Information Analysis Method

In this research, the opinions of project stakeholders and experts were used to complete the initial causal-disability model obtained from the literature review and obtain the final causal-disability model and confirm the research findings. Also, the opinions of these experts as well as the focal group of experts (which consists of at least 5 academic or industrial experts in the field of claims, which can be outside the experts and those involved in the studied project) were used to confirm the validity of the final model of system dynamics. Systems dynamics methodology is used for data analysis. Based on this, after formulating the dynamic hypothesis, with the summary that was done from the literature review and the comprehensive study of the past researches, a primary cause-effect model was extracted. Then this model was discussed with the stakeholders and experts of the studied projects and their opinions were obtained through in-depth semi-structured interviews. In order to properly analyze the data and extract the final causal model, the theme analysis method was used. After the approval of the final cause-disability model by the stakeholders and experts, the formulation of the model and the design of the flow chart of the model were done. After the approval of the flow diagram of the model by the experts and experts, and the validation tests of the model, simulation was performed and the effect of different policies was investigated and analyzed, and the behavior of the system was studied under different scenarios, and at the end, the findings of the analysis Various

policies and system behavior studies were discussed. "Vensim" software was used for simulation.

8. Descriptive Analysis

8.1. Frequency of samples according to gender variable

In this section, the descriptive findings of the research on the frequency distribution of the members of the statistical sample based on the gender variable have been presented. The findings related to the frequency distribution of the members of the statistical sample based on the gender variable are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Frequency distribution of statistical sample members based on gender variable

Cumulative frequency percentage	Abundance percentage	Abundance	Gender
60	60	9	Man
100	40	6	Female
	100	15	Total

As the findings presented in Table 2 show, 9 of the respondents (60%) are male and 6 of the respondents (40%) are female.

Chart 1: Frequency distribution of statistical sample members based on gender variable

In a similar way, it can be checked for the age and level of education variables.

9. Interviews with Experts

The semi-structured interview of experts is based on confirming or disconfirming each of the claims as follows:

Frequency distribution of samples based on the variable of lack of a strong employer body

In this section, the descriptive findings of the research on the frequency distribution of samples based on the variable of the absence of a strong employer body have been presented. The findings related to the frequency distribution of the members of the statistical sample based on the variable of the absence of a strong employer body are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of samples based on the variable of not having a strong employer body

Cumulative frequency percentage	Abundance percentage	Abundance	Confirm or reject
93	93	14	confirmation
100	7	1	rejection
	100	15	Total

As the findings presented in Table 3 show, 14 of the respondents (93%) have confirmed that the lack of a strong employer body is one of the claims, which indicates the general approval of this claim.

Chart 2: Frequency distribution of samples based on the variable of not having a strong employer body

In a similar way, it can be checked based on the variable of changes in the project and the variable of the initial demands of the employer and the variable of creating a redesign and the variable of creating a new work in some work fronts.

10. Identification of Claim Components with a Questionnaire-Based Claim Package Approach

Before calculating the mean and standard deviation of the claims score, the validity and reliability of the questionnaire obtained from the qualitative stage is first calculated and confirmed:

Table 3: Determining the content validity index of the questionnaire based on content validity ratio (CVR) and content validity index (CVI)

CVR	CVI	سؤال
0/81	0/92	1
0/84	0/88	2
0/85	0/86	3
0/86	0/89	4
0/89	0/90	5
0/84	0/87	6
0/83	0/86	7
0/84	0/89	8
0/85	0/88	9
0/83	0/90	10
0/84	0/87	11
0/83	0/86	12
0/81	0/82	13

Table 4: Confirmation of the reliability of the claims-based questionnaire

Cronbach's alpha coefficients	Claims
0/698	Lack of a strong employer body
0/702	Changes in the project
0/714	Changing the initial demands of the employer
0/726	Creating a redesign and sometimes changing the implementation method
0/673	Creating rework in some work fronts
0/706	Sudden stoppage of work by the contractor
0/715	Failure to fund the contractor by the employer
0/697	Delay in project completion
0/706	Violations in the construction process
0/711	Failure to observe justice in the terms of the parties' contract
0/693	Sudden change in the price of materials
0/706	Poor project management
0/677	Not including force majeure conditions in the contract

Since all Cronbach's alpha coefficients are higher than 0.6 and between 0.8, they indicate the good reliability of the questionnaire based on the claims.

In Table 5, the components of the claim are identified and confirmed by the members of the sample size in the quantitative stage with the claim package approach based on the questionnaire:

Table 5: Frequency distribution of samples based on other claims

Variance	standard deviation	Average	Claims
0.062	0.25	3.95	Lack of a strong employer body
0.129	0.36	3.86	Changes in the project
0.084	0.29	4.01	Changing the initial demands of the employer
0.032	0.18	3.99	Creating a redesign and sometimes changing the implementation method
0.052	0.23	3.92	Creating rework in some work fronts
0.072	0.27	4.16	Sudden stoppage of work by the contractor
0.115	0.34	3.99	Failure to fund the contractor by the employer
0.152	0.39	4.09	Delay in project completion
0.09	0.30	4.18	Violations in the construction process
0.067	0.26	4.00	Failure to observe justice in the terms of the parties' contract
0.048	0.22	3.98	Sudden change in the price of materials
0.084	0.29	4.11	Poor project management
0.136	0.37	4.04	Not including force majeure conditions in the contract

Now it is necessary to rank the claims raised in the questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale to determine the importance of each one in terms of priority. In Table 6, the 25th quartile, the 50th quartile or the median, and the 75th quartile are presented.

Table 6-Descriptive statistics of questionnaire responses

75th	50th	25th	Questions
3.74	2.20	1.83	First question
3.60	2.15	1.80	The second question
3.30	2.84	2.07	The third question
3.28	2.80	2.05	Fourth question
3.24	2.77	2.05	The fifth question
3.20	2.71	2.03	The sixth question
3.20	2.75	2.04	The seventh question
3.69	3.08	2.23	The eighth question
3.49	2.69	2.02	The ninth question
3.64	3.07	2.21	10th question
3.69	2.19	1.80	The eleventh question
3.14	2.66	2.02	The twelfth question
3.65	2.16	1.80	Thirteenth question

Table 7- Table of average ranks

rank number	average rank	Questions
10	2.49	First question
11	2.47	The second question
13	2.23	The third question
4	2.73	Fourth question
3	2.81	The fifth question
5	2.71	The sixth question
7	2.67	The seventh question
6	2.69	The eighth question
1	2.88	The ninth question
8	2.66	10th question
2	2.86	The eleventh question
12	2.26	The twelfth question
9	2.62	Thirteenth question

Table 8 - Table of ranks

Rank	Agents
1	Violations in the construction process
2	Sudden change in the price of materials
3	Creating rework in some work fronts
4	Creating a redesign and sometimes changing the implementation method
5	Sudden stoppage of work by the contractor
6	Delay in project completion
7	Failure to fund the contractor by the employer
8	Failure to observe justice in the terms of the parties' contract
9	Not including force majeure conditions in the contract
10	Lack of a strong employer body
11	Changes in the project
12	Poor project management
13	Changing the initial demands of the employer

11. Discussion

It is not possible to eliminate the possibility of claims in any project, but by identifying the main causes of claims and the relationship between them, they can be largely prevented from occurring in future projects. Construction projects are complex, unique and dynamic due to many influencing factors, high turnover, specialization and uniqueness of activities, workload, novelty and innovation, sensitivity, diverse locations and the involvement of different people in the project. On the other hand, the construction industry always faces problems that increase the time and cost of the project, and this is the reason why the project is not completed with the desired quality. Such conditions increase the possibility of lawsuits and disputes at different stages of project implementation.

Sometimes, after the occurrence of a claim, a lot of time will inevitably be spent to resolve it, and sometimes, due to the passage of time and problems getting old, various aspects are added to it and it becomes more complicated, and as a result, it causes more costs to the project. Considering that the number of claims in construction projects is increasing, determining the causes of claims and accurately understanding the complexity and relationships between the variables of creating a claim can be the main step in preventing and reducing claims. Therefore, although it is not possible to completely eliminate the possibility of claims occurring in projects, it can be prevented to a large extent by identifying the factors that cause it and examining the history of this category in previous projects. Certainly, preventing the occurrence of a dispute is much simpler and less expensive than resolving a dispute. If the causes of contractual disputes are known, it can be said that the ways to prevent them will also be known.

12. Answers to Questions

Answer to the first question

The first question has been that what are the main factors of dispute in the three-factor contracts for the construction of hospitals that lead to claims?

Based on the findings, it was determined that the absence of a strong employer body causes a weak contract both in terms of the contract strategy and in terms of the lack of sufficient initial studies (conceptual studies). With the start of the project, the weakness of the contract and the clarification of the stated shortcomings cause changes in the project and the initial demands of the employer. These changes have caused a redesign and sometimes a change in the implementation method, which itself causes rework in some work areas. The changes and rework made have reduced the efficiency and productivity of the contractor's team in the execution of the work, which itself causes rework. On the other hand, changes and rework will increase the volume and amount of work and create new work in the project, which will increase the cost. This increase in volume and new work due to changes and rework, etc., on the other hand, has increased the time, which will increase the cost of the project. The increase in time again causes a decrease in efficiency and productivity and also causes inflation due to the passage of time, which will again cause an increase in cost. Aggregation of cost increases will cause the employer's inability to finance the entire project, and with the claim of increased damages for delay in payment, the cost of the project will increase again. And the contractor's functions are paid late, which causes the late payment claim and also reduces the contractor's efficiency and productivity, which causes the extension of the project time. Again, the cycle of time extension and cost increase due to time increase and inflation is repeated, which causes the project cost to increase and will again cause a lack of funds for financing. Kanani (2018) in a research on the management of lawsuits and claims in the project with the perspective of private and urban constructions, the purpose of this article is to learn how to prevent common problems in procurement and resolve disputes between the employer and the contractor and, as a result, reduce time And the cost is to increase the efficiency and profitability of the project and achieve the desired benefits for the parties, and one of the claims raised in that research is the unnecessary increase in project cost and weakness in project management,

which is in line with the present research. Dana (2018) in a research entitled management of claims in projects, according to the existing standards, has reached the conclusion that the occurrence of changes in the project and the need for redesigns are among the important claims raised in the contracts, which is in line with the present research. Amani et al. (2018) in a research titled identifying the factors of claims in Iranian construction projects with the approach of three-factor contracts, have reached the conclusion that a significant part of the most frequent factors in the basic research is related to the employer. It was also found that some factors of claims occurrence in Iran are different from the results obtained from the analysis of the base researches, which are in line with the current research. Baqarpour and Mousavi (2017) in a research entitled providing an interpretative structural model for claim management in construction projects have reached the conclusion that the four reasons for choosing a contractor based on lower price and without considering technical competence and ability, the low price of the contract due to competition Above, ambiguity and contradiction in the documents or provisions of the contract and sudden and unexpected changes in the exchange rate and bank interest have the highest influence and influence on other causes and as a result have the highest importance in reducing and preventing the occurrence of claims, which is in line with the research. is present Salmani and Qurbani (2017) in a research titled claims management and identification of the main causes of claims in construction projects, reached the conclusion that among the most important issues and challenges that threaten the process of project implementation is the occurrence of claims in construction projects, which results such as breaking It will include relations, parties' differences and the most important delay in the project. In most projects, there is a possibility of claims from agents, especially contractors. These claims have negative effects on the implementation of projects. Although the possibility of these claims cannot be eliminated in any project, it is possible to largely prevent them from occurring in future projects by identifying the main causes of claims. which is in line with the present research.

Answer to the second research question

The second question of the current research was about the dynamic model of the claims system in DBB contracts. Based on the systems dynamics methodology, the present study has achieved a conceptual and basic model by reviewing the literature and past research, which has been approved by several experts. Then, based on that and the stated hypothesis of the research, an initial causal diagram based on the researcher's personal experiences in several DBB treatment projects will be drawn, and then the final causal diagram will be modified and finalized by conducting interviews and data analysis, and the flow diagram It will be built and the relationships between the variables of the model will be formulated by studying the literature and documentation of the projects, and the simulation in the case study and the scenario of different policies in the model will be done to reduce the claim.

Offers

- 1- Employing specialists in the subject of claims and using them in an institution called the Claims Management Office, in projects based on DBB contracts in treatment projects.

- 2- Approval of standard rules by the engineering system organization to consider solutions and notes for all the claims mentioned in the current research.
- 3- Modeling the structural equations of factors affecting the development of claims in DBB contracts

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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